

Condensation of 5-phenyl-2-chloroacetamido-1,3,4-oxadiazole with malonanilic acid hydrazide: (III; R=H)

General method: To a solution of 2-chloroacetamido-5-phenyl-oxadiazole (0.235 g; 0.001 mole) in absolute ethanol (20.0 ml), ethanolic solution of the acid hydrazide (0.285 g; 0.001 mole), pyridine (0.23 ml) and dimethyl formamide (0.2 ml) were added. The mixture was refluxed for ten hrs, ethanol was distilled off and the residue was washed successively with water and hot ethanol. The product was obtained as white crystals.

Yield: 0.11 g, (28.1%) m.p. 240°; Found: N, 21.28%. C₁₉H₁₈O₄N₆ requires N, 21.32%.

Biological activity: Biological activities of the new products are under investigation and shall be reported elsewhere.

TABLE I

Sl No.	Compound R I	m.p. °C	Yield %
1.	-H	218	76.9
2.	-Cl(o)	190	73.4
3.	-Cl(m)	215	38.9
4.	-Cl(p)	231	77.9
5.	-CH ₃ (o)	226	38.5
6.	-CH ₃ (m)	221	67.09
7.	-CH ₃ (p)	210	71.7
8.	-OCH ₃ (o)	230	57.70
9.	-OCH ₃ (m)	202	59.2
10.	-OCH ₃ (p)	225	57.90
R II			
1.	-H	147	69.30
2.	-Cl(p)	155	87.50
3.	-OH ₂ (p)	192	84.21
R III			
1.	-H	240	28.10
2.	-Cl(o)	227	18.20
3.	-Cl(m)	236	18.20
4.	-Cl(p)	232	18.20
5.	-CH ₃ (o)	238	14.03
6.	-CH ₃ (m)	236	12.70
7.	-CH ₃ (p)	235	12.70

Compound R I = Acid Hydrazones.

Compound R II = Iminophosphinic Acids.

Compound R III = N-(5-Phenyl-1,3,4-Oxadiazolo)-malon-unsubstituted/substituted-aniloyl-hydrazino acetamides.

All the products are white crystalline solids and gave satisfactory results of analysis.

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Chemical Constituents of *Elaeocarpus sikkimensis* Leaves

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Elaeocarpus sikkimensis (Family-*Elaeocarpaceae*) grows in the eastern Himalayas and in the hills of Sikkim and Assam upto a height of 5000 ft. In view of the medicinal uses of *E. ganitrus* and related species in the traditional system of medicine¹, several *Elaeocarpus* species have been investigated in our laboratory²⁻⁷ and in the present communication the chemical constituents of *E. sikkimensis* are reported.

Experimental

The air-dried and powdered leaves of the plant were extracted with ethanol (95%), the concentrated extract was adsorbed on paper pulp and extracted successively with petrol (60-80°), ether and ethyl acetate. The petrol extract on column chromatography over Al₂O₃ column yielded compound A and B. The ether extract on column chromatography over SiO₂ yielded compounds C, D and E and ethyl acetate extract yielded compound F.

Compound A was identified as β -sitosterol, m.p. 138° (acetate, m.p. 124°). The crystalline compound B, m.p. 288-89°, on acid hydrolysis furnished glucose (PC) and β -sitosterol (m.m.p., Co-TLC). Direct comparison (m.m.p., Co-TLC) with authentic sample established identity of the compound with β -sitosterol-D-glucoside⁸. Compound C, C₁₅H₁₀O₆ (M⁺, 286), m.p. 272-73°; $\lambda_{\max}$ 268, 368 nm (tetraacetate, m.p. 176-78°) was identified as kaempferol⁹. Compound D, C₁₅H₁₀O₇, m.p. 312°; $\lambda_{\max}$ 268, 272 nm furnished a penta methylether (M⁺, 372), m.p. 151°. Its identity with quercetin was settled by direct comparison (m.m.p., Co-TLC) with reference sample (Sigma). Compound E, C₇H₆O₆, m.p. 248° was recognised as gallic acid (triacetate, m.p. 163°) by direct comparison with authentic sample (E. Merck).

Compound F, crystallised from pyridine as straw-coloured needles, C₁₄H₆O₈, m.p. 350°; $\lambda_{\max}$

256, 300 nm; $\nu_{\max}$ 3840 (—OH), 1730 cm^{-1} (α -pyrone). It furnished a tetra-O-methyl ether indistinguishable from tetra-O-methyl ether of ellagic acid².

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Chemical Constituents from the Stem Heartwood of *Guazuma tomentosa*, Kunth (DC) and Stem of *Clerodendron indicum* (Linn) Kuntze

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PETROLEUM ether extract of stem heartwood of *Guazuma tomentosa* afforded friedelin, tetracosanoic acid, β -sitosterol and 3-O-acetyloleanolic acid while from the stems of *Clerodendron indicum* (24S)-ethylcholesta-5, 22, 25-triene-3 β -ol and β -sitosterol were isolated.

Guazuma tomentosa (Sterculiaceae) is a moderate sized tree, cultivated in gardens and is said to be of considerable medicinal value¹. A perusal of literature revealed that some work has been reported on its stem bark², leaves^{3,4} and flowers⁵.

Clerodendron indicum (Verbenaceae) is a large shrub, cultivated for ornamental purposes and is said to be of considerable medicinal value⁶. Leaves of this plant have already been studied by different workers^{7,8}.

The present note deals with the examination of stem heartwood and stems of *G. tomentosa* and *C. indicum* respectively.

Guazuma tomentosa: Completely dried and coarsely powdered stem heartwood (15 kg) of *G. tomentosa* was exhaustively extracted with petroleum ether (60-80°). The concentrated extract (10 g) was chromatographed over silica gel and eluted with petrol-benzene mixtures of different proportions when the following compounds were obtained. The identification of the compounds was made through m.p., mixed m.p., Co-tlc studies and preparation of some derivatives.

Friedelin: $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{50}\text{O}$ (M^+ , 426), m.p. 258-260° (petrol) (Lit.⁹ m.p. 260-262°); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 2950, 2890, 1725, 1470, 1380, 1360, 1230, 1190, 1120 cm^{-1} ; oxime, m.p. 290-292°; epifriedelinol, m.p. 276-277° by reduction with NaBH_4 .

Tetracosanoic acid: $\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{48}\text{O}_2$ (M^+ , 368), m.p. 87° (Me_2CO) (Lit.¹⁰ m.p. 87.5-88°); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 2900, 1705, 1480, 1300, 940, 730 and 720 cm^{-1} ; methyl ester, m.p. 58-59°.

β -*Sitosterol*: White needles m.p. 136-137° ($\text{CHCl}_3/\text{MeOH}$) (Lit.⁹ m.p. 136-137°); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3400, 2900, 2830, 1640, 1470, 1370, 1065 and 810 cm^{-1} ; acetate, m.p. 125-126°; benzoate m.p. 142-143°.

3-O-Acetyloleanolic acid: $\text{C}_{32}\text{H}_{50}\text{O}_4$ (M^+ , 498), m.p. 255° (petrol) (Lit.¹¹ m.p. 258-260°); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3300-3060, 1730, 1690, 1460, 1390, 1325, 1030, 970, 900, 800 cm^{-1} ; methyl ester, m.p. 221°; oleanolic acid, m.p. 305° by alkali hydrolysis.

Clerodendron indicum: Air dried and coarsely powdered stems (5 kg) of *C. indicum* were extracted with petroleum ether (60-80°) and the concentrated extract (6 g) was chromatographed over silica gel when the following compounds were obtained. The compounds were identified by direct comparison (m.m.p., Co-tlc, ir) with authentic samples.

(24S)-*Ethylcholesta-5,22,25-triene-3-ol*: $\text{C}_{29}\text{H}_{48}\text{O}$ (M^+ , 410), m.p. 148° (petrol) (Lit.⁹ m.p. 151-153°); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3450, 3230, 2950, 1640, 1190, 1135, 1060, 1030, 960, 885 and 800 cm^{-1} ; acetate m.p. 140°.

β -*Sitosterol*: Colourless flakes, m.p. 136-137° ($\text{CHCl}_3/\text{MeOH}$); acetate m.p. 124-125°; benzoate m.p. 143-144°.

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